

THE ORGANIZED INSTRUCTIONAL SYSTEM FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICAL KNOWLEDGE AMONG PROSPECTIVE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article develops an organized learning system for developing the medical knowledge of future physical education teachers and highlights important requirements for organizing lessons to reinforce medical knowledge, including the appropriate selection of lesson formats, tools, and methods.*

Keywords: *future physical education teachers, developing medical knowledge, lesson, format, method, tool, learning system, discussion, education, oral, written, reinforcement.*

Introduction

This article develops an organized learning system for developing the medical knowledge of future physical education teachers, which primarily serves to provide students with high-quality and engaging learning (see Figure 1).

The correct selection of methods in the educational process is also an important issue. Teaching methods are determined primarily by the goals and objectives set for the course, the conscious and thorough acquisition of knowledge, skills, and abilities by students, the development of creativity and independence, and the objectives. One of the key requirements for organizing lessons aimed at reinforcing medical knowledge is the diversity of methods and their relevance to a specific purpose. Oral, written, and practical methods are widely used in the educational process [1].

It is widely acknowledged that oral methods are the most common and widespread method in all educational institutions. This method is also called the logical method and is implemented in the form of storytelling, conversation, explanation, and lecture. In this case, the oral presentation of educational material serves not only to impart knowledge to students but also to spark their interest in the same subject. Written and practical methods reinforce the theoretical knowledge acquired by students. The effectiveness of teaching also depends on the methods used. First, let's examine the broader meaning of the concept of method, that is, its composition as a set of methods and techniques. Using these methods and techniques, the teacher provides students with knowledge aimed at achieving a specific goal, develops the necessary skills and abilities, strengthens them, and assesses their level of mastery. Students actively and consciously master these skills and abilities, acquiring medical knowledge [2].

Individualized instruction can be used when most students in a lesson are completing work that is different in process but similar in content. For example, it is necessary to teach medical examinations and medical tests in depth. In such cases, the teacher analyzes topic plans for preparation and, in advance, distinguishes between general signs (information) that will be

presented to students in a frontal format and information that will be presented using an individual format [3].

Figure 1. The organized training system for developing the medical knowledge of future physical education teachers

In this case, more information will be presented individually. Clearly, when organizing a lesson based on an individual format, the teacher will have to do more preparation. Ultimately, a blended lesson will consist of elements of the three lesson formats mentioned above. It should also be noted that, depending on the content of the curriculum, the nature of the specialization, and other factors, other organizational formats may be used in education.

It is known that teaching methods have been classified and defined by educational researchers in various ways. The most common and acceptable classification is as follows: oral methods, written methods, practical methods, and heuristic methods.

Narrative is a method of presenting educational material in a lively, figurative manner. The story should be linked to the students' monitoring and ongoing work. The story should conclude with a brief summary of the lesson topic. Lively speech is used in any method; various aspects are explained through lively speech, work-based methods, displays, and aids.

Teacher speech is essential to ensure active learning, prevent errors, assist students in performing the same work procedure, modify equipment control structures, and change control methods [4].

Oral presentation of educational material through explanation represents a sequential presentation of the main material. Analysis and evidence play a significant role. The teacher uses their own notes and calculations in their presentation, thereby clarifying the essence of the current work. When presenting educational material, the teacher should rely on the students' level of theoretical knowledge and their experience gained during industrial training [5].

Speaking practice - in this case, students answer the teacher's question or express themselves in accordance with the content of the question. Speaking practice is used when students have a certain amount of knowledge on the material being studied. At the end of speaking practice, the teacher summarizes the students' answers. Speaking practice is one of the convenient and effective teaching methods that develops students' mental activity and attention to technology. The conversation can be conducted in the form of a discussion of specific issues based on a pre-prepared plan and students' answers to questions posed by the teacher. The success of a conversation often depends on the teacher's ability to ask students the right questions. Conversations should be conducted in a way that facilitates the successful achievement of established educational and developmental objectives. Conversations should be aimed at a clearly defined goal.

The demonstration method involves the display of equipment, exhibits, educational films, videos, slides, etc. Presentations prepared by the teacher or student are essential for enriching the lesson content.

Teaching and methodological resources are methods and tools used in the learning process. They help develop students' knowledge, skills, and competencies. The following information was collected during a study of selected lectures, seminars, laboratory work, and other teaching methods [6].

Primary education: In this method, the teacher conducts the lesson with their participation, and students primarily act as observers;

Active learning: Students actively participate and learn through activities such as group work, discussions, and project creation;

Laboratory work: Gaining practical knowledge through scientific experiments that can be used;

Project-based method: Students gain experience by completing a project on a specific topic;

Simulation and role-playing: Modeling real-life situations by participating in various situations;

Problem solving: Developing thinking skills through solving mathematical or logical problems;

Internet and multimedia resources: Learning using websites, videos, and interactive courses;

Case studies: Developing problem-solving skills through analyzing real-life situations.

It can be observed that each of these methods has its own advantages and disadvantages, and their effectiveness depends on the context in which they are used. It is important to consider the student's goals, needs, and interests in order to choose the right methods.

It can be seen that several works by scientists who have developed various methods of knowledge development in medical education for students. Ivan Petrovich Pavlov [7] is a physiologist and Nobel laureate who is considered one of the scientists who made a significant contribution to the understanding of the learning process through the study of conditioned reflexes. Antonio Gaudi [8] is known for his innovative approaches to architecture and medical education, and his works are of great importance in the design of medical institutions. Benjamin Spock [9] is a pediatrician and youth health specialist who proposed new methods of raising children in his "Book of Sport". Frederick Perls [10] is one of the founders of Gestalt therapy, who created the theoretical foundations in psychology and medical education. Aldous Huxley [11] is one of the scientists who discussed education, health, and human development in their works. Among the scientists who laid the foundations for educational methods in sports medicine, several important figures stand out.

Among them, Alexander Bakulev [12] is known for his scientific developments in the fields of sports medicine and cardiology, and his achievements are incomparable. Georgy Fedorov [13] made a significant contribution to the development of physiology and rehabilitation methods in sports medicine and wrote several books to facilitate student learning. Yuri Sukharev [14] is a specialist in sports traumatology and rehabilitation, particularly in physical education classes, where he presented injuries and their recovery, care, and therapeutic measures in a variety of diagrams, figures, and tables in a format understandable to students. Kirill Lebedev [15] conducted scientific research on the effective organization of medical care during sporting events.

In conclusion, it can be said that if an organized educational system for developing the medical knowledge of future physical education teachers is carefully designed, then lessons will be conducted at a high level. Each lesson will be effective if the form, method, tools, and teaching methods are used correctly.

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